
Influence of Cognitive Development and Learning Strategies Among Toddlers in Primary Schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study ascertains the influence of cognitive development and learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Two objectives, research questions and null hypotheses were raised and tested in the study. The study adopted an ex-post factor research design. The population of the study was 118,106, out of which 383 toddlers were sampled. The data were analysed using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to test all the hypotheses. The findings revealed that a significant relationship exists between cognitive development and learning strategies, as indicated by ($r = .142, p = .006$). Also, a significant relationship exists between cognitive development and intelligence and learning strategies among toddlers as indicated by ($r = .241, p = .000$); it was concluded that cognitive development may influence intelligence and learning strategies among toddlers. Finally, the study recommends that curriculum planners can use Piaget's stages to design developmentally appropriate learning activities so as to match the cognitive abilities of the pupils at each stage in primary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Keywords: Cognitive development, Learning strategies, Toddlers, Intelligence, Piaget's stages of development

Introduction

Cognitive psychologists Piaget, Brunner and Guthrie, among others, view cognitive development to include the total process, such as language, perception, memory, problem-solving and decision-making. The development of these activities has been shown to start even before birth and is known to continue throughout one's life. Piaget (2014) opined that one aspect of cognitive development is *perception*, which is the integration, interpretation and understanding of sensory stimuli. Driscoll (2001) stated that young children have the capacity to receive signals and react in more than a reflexive fashion. As a result of cognitive development, all children seem to have the potential to learn any language after birth. A typical pattern of language production includes cooing, followed by babbling, then one-word utterances, short “telegraphic speech” patterns, longer phrases, longer sentences and finally by about four years.

Cognitive psychologists view language acquisition as the primary basis for thinking and memory.

Wadworth (1996) stated that one of the most influential approaches to understanding cognitive development was proposed by Piaget (1896-1980), who had been working on child development for more than the last 40 years. Two concepts are crucial to all the stages in his theory; the first stage is called the sensorimotor period, when the infant learns and develops sensorimotor skills by manipulating objects in his environment. In the second stage, which runs from two to seven years, the child begins to acquire vocabulary with which he represents objects and experiences he perceives. Similarly, Wood (2008) observed in a study conducted by Piaget of his own biological child that the child can extract concepts from experience and can manipulate objects in his mind. In the concrete operational period, which begins at seven and continues up to 12 years of age, the child begins to think logically and rationally about problems which he faces. In assimilation, a child's ability to incorporate incoming material into already existing schema (concepts of the world) can also boost the intelligence of the child. As he encounters new experiences, he assimilates them into existing schemas or accommodates by modifying his existing mental structures. Caluag (2002) highlighted that Piaget's theories stress the sequence of events in cognitive development. The ages are suggested as average or typical but not necessarily binding. Wood (2008) observed that Piaget, in his theory, suggested that providing children with tasks and activities that slightly exceed their current cognitive abilities can promote cognitive development.

The information processing approach to cognitive development as occurring in stages by Piaget is that cognitive development is an active process of continuous increase in language, verbal fluency, numerical skills, knowledge, memory, ability to solve problems and proficiency in applying these skills in various circumstances. Adejumo (2010) also emphasises that, in Piaget's theories, information-processing approaches envision changing conceptualisations of the world as a child becomes increasingly sophisticated in cognitive skills. However, information-processing approaches do not propose stages or establish cut-off points for the behaviours being observed, emphasising instead the changes in efficiency and understanding with which information is processed.

Boyes (2013) stated that Piaget, a prominent psychologist who explores how individuals, particularly children, think and construct their understanding of the world, believes that children are active learners who actively engage with their environment for the progressive changes in cognitive processes.

The cortex is the conscious, rational-thinking part of the brain and determines the child's response to certain situations. Research carried out by Geekz (2014) revealed that if an infant is constantly being subjected to negative situations, experiencing domestic violence and/or neglect, then the connections that form the cortex to help deal with situations in a rational way are limited. In situations such as that, the child is left to rely on the limbic system, which is the body's alarm system. So, when a child is faced with a mild situation, for example, the person sitting next to them takes their pencil without asking; instead of the rational-thinking cortex being engaged, the limbic system is triggered, displaying the flight/fight reaction. 'Learning strategies' refers to behaviour intended or thoughts that influence the ability to select, acquire, organise, and integrate new knowledge (Weinstein & Mayer, 1986, in Dauda (2023)).

The learning strategies as a systematic plan involve the rehearsal strategy and the elaboration strategy. Organisations that are designed to teach learners how to learn and thought processes affect behaviour that is consciously invoked by learners to facilitate knowledge acquisition and to manage and regulate information in the learning process. Cognitive learning strategies are associated with the actual processing of information coming from the environment to transform it into knowledge. Therefore, cognitive strategies directly promote effective learning among learners. Meta-cognitive strategies, on the other hand, influence information processing indirectly by regulating and supporting the cognitive information processing strategies (Hawley 2006; Lopez 2001; Weinstein & Hume 1998). Therefore, the earlier cognitive researchers gained more knowledge from instruction strategies in reading comprehension, which is regarded as the core of effective learning and development and is the most essential element in the education of the child. Therefore, finding ways of teaching learners comprehension strategies so as to enable them process texts in a manner that will facilitate understanding, retention and retrieval of information is considered to be crucial (Mayer 2001; Van Keer & Verhaeghe 2005).

(Lopez 2001, Monteith 2001, Weinstein & Hume 1998) identified the general cognitive learning strategies: attention, rehearsal, elaboration and organisation. According to Carnegie and Hawes (1989), learning strategies are conceptualised in terms of the levels at which learners tend to reinforce the natural information-processing activities, namely by using the deep approach or the surface approach, or as processes that occur in stages in certain parts of the brain.

Statement of the Problem

The poor academic performance of primary school pupils has become a major concern to stakeholders in the education sector, prompting an urgent search for sustainable

solutions. There is widespread public outcry over the perceived decline in educational standards from year to year, which has been attributed to several factors, including frequent changes in teachers, classroom conditions, school environments, and pupils' academic performance. A critical issue underlying these challenges is the inadequate cognitive development of pupils, which negatively affects their learning outcomes.

In view of this situation, serious attention needs to be given to factors that can enhance effective learning at the primary school level. The declining performance of pupils has raised public concern regarding who should be held responsible for the apparent deterioration in educational standards. Reports have indicated systemic challenges within the education sector. For instance, according to ICIR (2020), a number of workers in Kaduna State were disengaged due to lack of relevant qualifications. Similarly, Kaduna State dismissed 213 teachers over the possession of fake certificates, while several others were disengaged after failing competency tests (asenexpress.com, 2021).

The researcher, having previously served as a primary school teacher, observed that the presence of conservative, inexperienced, and unqualified teachers in the profession constitutes a significant factor contributing to the falling standard of education. These challenges further limit teachers' ability to support pupils' cognitive development and the effective use of appropriate learning strategies.

Against this background, the present study seeks to determine the influence of cognitive development and learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to ascertain the influence of cognitive development and learning strategies among the toddlers in primary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the present study are to:

- i. Determine the relationship between cognitive development and learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State.
- ii. Ascertain the influence of learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Research questions

The following research questions were raised:

- i. What is the relationship of cognitive development and learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State?
- ii. Do cognitive development and intelligence have influence on learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

- i. There is no significant relationship between cognitive development and learning strategies among toddlers in Zaria metropolis primary schools, Kaduna state.
- ii. There is no significant influence of cognitive development and intelligence on learning strategies among toddlers in primary school in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State.

Methodology

The study adopted an ex-post facto research design to investigate the influence of cognitive development and learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State. This design was considered appropriate because it examines existing conditions and relationships without any manipulation of variables by the researcher. The variables under study had already occurred and could not be controlled or altered. The participants were not randomly selected; rather, they were selected based on their stages of cognitive development and observable characteristics of intelligence among the toddlers.

A questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The sampling process was guided by the recommendation of Krejcie and Morgan (1970), which suggests that 10% of a population above 500 is sufficient for generalization. Prior to the main study, a pilot test was conducted to determine the reliability of the instrument. The pilot study was carried out at Zaria Children School, GRA Zaria, which was not included in the sampled schools. Thirty copies of the questionnaire were administered with the assistance of two teachers serving as research assistants, and the completed instruments were retrieved immediately after administration. The data obtained from the pilot study were analyzed to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument.

The instrument was validated by experts from the Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, to ensure its content and construct validity. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.74, indicating that the instrument was reliable for the study. This is consistent with the view of Akinade and Awolobi (2010), who noted

that Cronbach's alpha values range between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating greater reliability for data collection.

The data collected for the main study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was employed to test all the hypotheses formulated for the study to determine the presence or absence of significant relationships among the variables. All hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The analyses of the results which compared the relationship in scores among toddlers in primary schools were presented in the following tables:

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between cognitive development and learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Primary Schools Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Table 1: Pearson Product–Moment Correlation (r) Showing the Relationship Between Cognitive Development and Learning Strategies among Toddlers in Primary Schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	SD	R	P
Cognitive devlp		383	3,72	6.08	
	7	8		1.42	0.06
Learning strategies		383	31.75	9.30	

Table 1 reveals that a relationship exists between cognitive development and learning strategies among pupils, as indicated by the correlation coefficient ($r = .142$) and the p-value (.006), which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. This result implies that higher levels of cognitive development are associated with improved learning strategies, and vice versa. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant relationship between cognitive development and learning strategies among pupils, is hereby rejected.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship between cognitive development and intelligence on learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools, Zaria, Kaduna state

Table 2: Pearson Product–Moment Correlation (r) Showing the Relationship Between Cognitive Development and Intelligence in Relation to Learning Strategies among Toddlers in Primary Schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	P
Cog D & Intgc	383	26.818	5.871	.241	.000
Learning Strategies	383	31.75	9.30		

Table 2 reveals that a significant relationship exists between cognitive development and intelligence in relation to learning strategies among toddlers, as indicated by the correlation coefficient ($r = .241$) and the p-value (.000), which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. The correlation coefficient further indicates that higher levels of cognitive development and intelligence are associated with more effective learning strategies, which may positively influence learning outcomes. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between cognitive development and intelligence in relation to learning strategies is hereby rejected.

Discussion

The results of this study revealed that a significant relationship exists among cognitive development, intelligence, and learning strategies among toddlers in primary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State. This finding corroborates the study of Boyes (2013), who reported a significant relationship between cognitive development and intelligence, noting that cognitive development enhances a child's ability to judge, reason effectively, and perceive the environment more accurately. This implies that children's behaviour is largely influenced by their thinking processes.

Similarly, Piaget emphasised the importance of play in children's intellectual development, arguing that play enables children to experiment with their environment and practise new skills, thereby fostering cognitive growth. Through play-based activities, children actively construct knowledge, which enhances their cognitive abilities and supports the development of effective learning strategies.

The findings of the present study further revealed that toddlers' cognitive development is generally influenced by intelligence and memory as mediated by learning strategies. This result aligns with the study of Sambo (2014), who posited that intelligence comprises a general factor (g-factor) underlying all mental activities, as well as multiple specific factors (s-factors) related to particular tasks. These factors collectively contribute to enhanced learning and improved academic outcomes among young learners.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was established that toddlers' cognitive development and intelligence are significantly correlated with learning strategies. This implies that appropriate learning strategies enhance toddlers' ability to learn more effectively and improve their overall performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are made. Curriculum planners should utilize Piaget's stages of cognitive development in designing developmentally appropriate learning activities that align with the cognitive abilities of primary school pupils in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. This will ensure that instructional content and methods are suited to pupils' developmental levels and enhance effective learning.

Caregivers, psychologists, counsellors, and educators should recognize that children progress through cognitive and behavioural stages at their own pace. With this understanding, they can provide appropriate guidance and support that caters to the individual learning needs of pupils and promotes optimal cognitive development.

Parents should also actively involve themselves in activities that support and promote their children's learning, problem-solving, and decision-making skills. Such involvement will reinforce learning at home and contribute positively to pupils' overall cognitive and academic development.

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